

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF LINGUISTICS, THE IMPORTANCE OF STUDY

Yunusova Shakhnoza Mukhamedumarovna

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami Senior teacher of the
Department of General Linguistics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6382220>

Annotation: Language is only a product of personality society. Without language, it is impossible to know, study any reality and phenomenon, the role of man in nature, in society, the ways of the development of society. Linguistics or linguistic knowledge (linguistics is an independent and clear science about language, studies the origin of language, the processes and laws of historical development on a scientific basis. This science consists of certain and general linguistics. A certain (private) linguistics studies the dictionary composition, phonetic system and grammatical construction of a particular language, the ways of development and its relation to fraternal languages on a scientific basis and in this way examines the dictionary wealth, phonetics of the language, creates scientific knowledge.

Keywords: Linguistics, the importance of Science, study, purpose, functions, techniques, development, progress.

Language is a social phenomenon. Language has arisen in the process of Community Development. Language is not a natural, biological phenomenon, the existence of a language and its development is not subject to the laws of nature. Language serves the universal interest as the product of evolutionary periods in the process of the history of society as a whole.

And general linguistics studies the origin, social essence, role and function in society, the way of development, the interdependence of thinking with language, the interaction of language and creates methods of checking linguistics. General Linguistics studies some linguistics, a group of linguistics and fraternal linguistics, summarizes the phenomenon of language, language evidence identified as a result of examination, makes scientific conclusions and on this basis determines the legalities of language. Apparently, linguistics is an independent science that studies the human language. Linguistics initially arose as a science of practical importance, now it has become a science of pure theoretical character. Mankind, saying goodbye to the XX century, stepped into the third millennium. To this day, mankind has made great strides in all spheres of social life. Adam created a lot of news with his intelligence and diligence. Among the spiritual riches, the knowledge accumulated in the science of linguistics plays an important role. There will be great linguists of each era. They put forward their thoughts about the language of their land and people. Knowledge of linguistics is of great importance in the transformation of ideas into ideology of a certain period, which manifests itself as a flag that leads the people towards Great Goals.

In linguistics, the direction in which it is intended to illuminate the internal relations, interconnectedness of language components, the structural side of the language, is called structural linguistics. Private (concrete) linguistics studies the phonetic system of each specific language, the composition of the dictionary, the construction of the dictionary and the ways of their development and the attitude of this language to other languages and on this basis strives to create the scientific knowledge of the concrete language. General Linguistics

studies such issues as the laws of language in general, the emergence of language, the role and function of language in society, and not a particular language. Also in this science, the languages identified as a result of the study of concrete languages, language groups, fraternal languages are summarized and important scientific and theoretical conclusions are drawn.

General linguistics is a science that studies the human language scientifically, its main purpose is to provide information about the subject and tasks of linguistics, the essence of language, the structure of language, language and speech, language and thought, the system of characters in language, language and society, language development, schools and directions of linguistics, methods of scientific research of languages. In this process, the typological signs of the language are determined. The science of General Linguistics studies such problems as the nature and essence of language, the relationship of language with society and thought, the structure and systematic nature of language, the laws of origin and development of language, the typology and classification of languages, language learning techniques. The fields of linguistics that study linguistic issues in a practical way are considered as Applied Linguistics. He has such directions as experimental phonetics, linguistic analysis, lexicography. Language is the most important weapon of the relationship between people, formed in the process of the development of society and serves universal interests. Since the emergence and development of language is associated with the development of society, the source of the study of all sciences that think about human perfection is considered to be related to language. The nature, essence of language requires scientific study of such important issues as the function, structure and interaction of the elements that make up this structure, its internal mechanism, the principles of performance in a person society, research in all aspects.

Language is the product of the Society of personality. Without language, it is impossible to know, study any reality and phenomenon, the position of man in Nature, Society, the ways of the development of society. It is known that the natural human language is a complex subject that is studied not only in linguistics, but also by a number of other sciences, and the definition that each science gives to the language can also be different. Even in the science of linguistics itself, there is no single definition of language. The question of the definition of language is one of the most important issues in the history of linguistics, which has been interpreted differently in the history of Science and is now causing sharp controversy among various scientific schools and currents.

In fact, every theory that exists in linguistics is based primarily on language how to understand. Language how to understand is important in creating a theory about language. To a certain extent, issues such as the subject, subject and method of scientific study of linguistics depend on how to understand it. Language different definitions in the history of linguistics also caused a different reflection of the subject of science. Therefore, it is worthwhile to consider how this issue was solved in the main stages of the history of linguistics.

In conclusion, the subject of linguistics is a complex system –language, the source of which has its own internal laws of study. The study of the peculiarities of the language, the laws of development makes it possible to give a comprehensive description of this social phenomenon. Language is a system of specific symbols subordinate to the general law, communication in the Society of personality is the most important weapon of attitude, expression of thought and the basis of thinking, the means of conveying reality from

generation to generation, expressing human experiences, feelings. In the history of linguistics, it is possible to observe different approaches to the language.

REFERENCES:

1. Iriskulov M. Introduction to linguistics. - T., 2008.
2. Yoldoshev I. , Sharipov O'. Introduction to linguistics. - T., 2007.
3. Yoldashev I., Muhamedova S., Sharipova O`, Madjidova R. Basics of linguistics. - T., 2013.
4. Mechkovskaya N. B. General Linguistics, structural and social typology of languages. - T., 2006